

Milestone 29: Completion of 2nd programme revision with WP4-6 recommendation

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ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

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there will need to be consideration of the availability of access units from the NFs to accommodate the substantial requirements of the WP6 satellite cal / val pilot. Whilst there may be impact on the availability of access provision from affected NFs within the calls, there is no impact on the proposed timetable. WP7 will continue discussions and provide potential revisions at the next milestone (MS32, Month 36). Until that time, the timeline and program will remain unchanged, as illustrated on the official website (Table 2).

Table 2. Current timetable and programme of ATMO-ACCESS as illustrated in the project’s website.